

GUEST EDITORIAL

Isopathy: nostrum or nocebo? Where now?

D Reilly^{1*}

¹Glasgow Homoeopathic Hospital, 1053 Great Western Road, Glasgow, UK

Isopathy courts controversy, and where there is controversy there is a chance of creativity. In the 1980s, in the guise of allergen immunotherapy, isopathy helped launch the stormy debate on 'homeopathy vs placebo' into the scientific arena.^{1–3} This won it friends and enemies: a response familiar over the nearly two centuries of use of isopathy by homeopaths. Around a 100 y earlier, in 1881, Lippe described this approach of prescribing homeopathic preparations of causative agents (as opposed to similars) as 'a fatal error', 60 y after Lux had first used isopathy in 1820 for animal epidemics.⁴ Hahnemann cleverly circumvented the issues around 'identicals' by saying they ceased to be so when changed by potentisation. Nevertheless, he thought using a human disease substance to treat that disease (say the use of *Psorinum* to treat scabies) was 'going too far—nothing can come of it but misfortune and aggravation of the disease'.⁵ Yet that is exactly what people as skilled as Hering did, using *Psorinum* in scabies—and today the range of practitioners, styles and applications is extensive—using the spectrum of infectious agents to toxins to allergens⁶—chosen by diagnosis, test, environmental considerations or pathophysiology. Still homeopaths, like their medicines, seem stronger in division and isopathy is shunned or ignored, by many.

So does isopathy work, is it safe, how is it best used, how does it compare, is it suppressive? With so many critical questions, can we even say that we are over the first hurdle? Have the randomised placebo controlled trials scaled the culturally heightened barrier labelled 'intrinsic activity in homeopathic dilutions?' never mind the narrower issue of the use of isopathy? Perhaps the answer depends on who the judge is, but it is true that whatever one makes of the recent meta-analyses^{7,8} within them the isopathic studies have tended to fare well, and they do have a number of methodological advantages when tackling 'the placebo issue'.

The two interesting trials of isopathy from Aabel and colleagues in this edition of the BHJ^{9,10} nudge us a little further forward, though the pace can be dispiritingly slow for researchers who have put in the enormous effort that such work demands. Their birch allergy treatment study, which they point out is likely underpowered, nevertheless found 'a clinically interesting difference' between homeopathy and placebo, but the prophylactic study was all but washed out by the weather conspiring to offer them only a three day window for pollen to enter. But both studies have a common finding which might be important—possible initial aggravations. This data adds weight to the similar reactions reported in the Glasgow team's isopathy trials. (The fourth and final trial of the 'Is Homeopathy a Placebo Response?' series is currently in press with the *British Medical Journal* and again shows significantly more aggravations from homeopathy than placebo.¹¹) This isopathic retelling of the old story of aggravations¹² might in the long run prove of more value in the scientific debate than the study of therapeutic effects. We could reframe the question to ask 'Is Homeopathy a Nocebo Response?' and use aggravation phenomena to test the placebo hypothesis. (Nocebo reactions are adverse effects from a placebo.) In designing any such work some factors are worth bearing in mind. First, nocebo responses are not uncommon and can be intense. Second, we must be aware of the potential in homeopathy for enhanced nocebo responses—for example, from the 'pre-hypnotic' cultural and clinical context of the expectations of 'getting worse before getting better'. Modification of the context can even lead to differing reactions to identical placebos in the same patient over time.¹³ We will still need double blinding to help us with this. Meanwhile, on the therapeutic front, future trials of isopathy need to be of significantly larger scale, but more importantly, we should avoid any more large scale studies without initial pilots of the methods and models to be tested. There are too many examples of wasted effort in 'repeats' of studies which change some aspect of what they are trying to replicate.

On a parallel front we need to forge into the clinical arena, determining safety and effectiveness—as in

*Correspondence: Dr D Reilly, Glasgow Homoeopathic Hospital, 1053 Great Western Road, Glasgow G12 0XQ, UK.

the current Glasgow study comparing different potency and repetition regimes.¹⁴ Caution is required and the overall medical management of our patients is critical. Isopathy is sometimes used in the care of patients with unstable allergic conditions, circumstances where even placebo can be harmful, for example impacting on asthma intensity.¹³ There is no evidence to date of fatal reactions to isopathy, but we should remain alert—conventional desensitisation is fatal in around only 1 in 25000 uses.¹⁵

With further study isopathy might prove its worth as a credible first line alternative to conventional desensitisation. No doubt it will provoke more creative controversy on route.

References

- 1 Reilly DT, Taylor MA. Potent placebo or potency? A proposed study model with initial findings using homeopathically prepared pollens in hay fever. *Br Hom J* 1985; **74**: 65–75.
- 2 Reilly DT, Taylor MA, McSharry C, Aitchison T. Is homeopathy a placebo response? Controlled trial of homeopathic potency, with pollen in hayfever as model. *Lancet* 1986; **ii**: 881–886.
- 3 Reilly DT, Taylor MA, Beattie NGM, *et al.* Is evidence for homeopathy reproducible? *Lancet* 1994; **344**: 1601–1606.
- 4 Quoted in: Gladish DG. *The Homoeopathic Recorder* 1952; **47**: 204–207.

- 5 Hahnemann S. *Organon of Medicine*, 6th edn. London: Victor Gollancz, 1983, 1842 Paragraph 56.
- 6 Rost J. Homeopathy—isonopathy. *Br Hom J* 1986; **75**: 6–9.
- 7 Linde K, Clausius N, Ramirez G, *et al.* Are the clinical effects of homeopathy placebo effects? A meta-analysis of placebo-controlled trials. *Lancet* 1997; **350**: 834–843.
- 8 Homoeopathic Medicine Research Group. Report to the European Commission—Directorate General XII: Science, Research and Development. vol 1: short version, chapters 1–7: 16–171996. European Commission, Brussels.
- 9 Aabel S, Laerum E, Dølvik S, Djupesland P. Is homeopathic 'immunotherapy' effective? A double-blind, placebo-controlled trial with the isopathic remedy *Betula 30c* for patients with birch pollen allergy. *Br Hom J* 2000; **89**: 161–168.
- 10 Aabel S. No beneficial effect of isopathic prophylactic treatment for birch pollen allergy during a low pollen season. *Br Hom J* 2000; **89**: 169–173.
- 11 Taylor MA, Reilly D, Llewellyn-Jones RH, McSharry C, Aitchison TC. Randomised controlled trial of homeopathy versus placebo in perennial allergic rhinitis with overview of four trial series. *Br Med J* 2000; **321**: 471–476.
- 12 Hahnemann H. Essay on a new principle for ascertaining curative powers of drugs and some examinations of the previous principles. *Hufeland's Journal* 1796; **II**: 391–439, 465–561.
- 13 Reilly DT, Taylor MA. Individual patients and their responses—OPICS. *Complementary Therapies in Medicine* 1993; **1**(Suppl 1): 1–50.
- 14 Kayne SB, Beattie N. The use of isopathy in the treatment of allergies. Proceedings of the 55th Congress LMHI; Budapest, 2000, p 30.
- 15 Committee of the Safety of Medicines. CSM update: desensitisation vaccines. *Br Med J* 1986; **293**: 948.